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Thema

Kommission IV: Bodenfruchtbarkeit und Pflanzenernährung

Biogeochemie gekoppelter Stoffkreisläufe (NPK) unter traditioneller Landnutzung

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Titel

The current state of soil cover in Kazakhstan, problems and solution

Abstract

The main directions of scientific activity of the U.U.Uspanov Kazakh Research Institute of Soil Science and Agrochemistry is study of regularities in soil formation under anthropogenic pressure; rational use and increase of bio-productivity of soil resources; development of new technologies to improve soil fertility and crop productivity; assessment of the ecological state of soils in the conditions of anthropogenesis and development of measures for their improvement; provision of consulting and practical services for survey and preparation of agrochemical cartograms and map- schemes with various scales.